

MULTIMINER - INNOVATIVE EARTH OBSERVATION METHODS FOR MINERAL EXPLORATION AND MINE SITE MONITORING

by

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The European Union aims to become a carbon-neutral economy by 2050, necessitating an industry transformation in the raw materials sector to ensure a sustainable supply of critical (CRM) and strategic (SRM) raw materials. The EU Action Plan for CRM 2020 and the CRM Act of 2023 outline specific actions to mitigate supply risks, protect the environment, and secure the EU's strategic autonomy in the raw materials market. These initiatives, along with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and several international, and state level regulations, emphasize the integration of sustainability and circularity principles across the sector.

The Horizon Europe funded Research and Innovation Action project “Multi-source and Multi-scale Earth observation and Novel Machine Learning Methods for Mineral Exploration and Mine Site Monitoring” (**MultiMiner**, 2023–2026, Grant number 101091374) aims to enhance the efficiency of mineral exploration and mine site monitoring through the development of innovative, highly automated data processing algorithms (Figure 1). These solutions leverage Earth Observation (EO) technologies and novel machine learning methods, requiring minimal *in situ* reference data. MultiMiner's EO-based exploration solutions have very low environmental impact. They improve safety and are environmentally safe, making them potentially more socially acceptable than traditional CRM exploration methods. MultiMiner's solutions for mine site monitoring increase the transparency of mining operations by offering new and innovative tools for the detection of environmental impacts.

The project demonstrates the applicability of its algorithms through case studies at five European test sites (Hochfilzen, Austria; Ihalainen, Finland; Kallyntiri, Chalkidiki and Kirki; Greece), utilizing data from sources like Copernicus Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, EnMAP, and drone-borne hyperspectral, radiometric and multiband SAR sensors. These case studies validate the effectiveness of MultiMiner's solutions in real-world mining and exploration environments, ultimately contributing to the EU's autonomy in raw materials and promoting environmentally sustainable mining practices.

Figure 1. The MultiMiner project focuses on developing EO data using unsupervised and weakly supervised Machine Learning approaches for a wide range of applications in mineral exploration and mine site monitoring.

The MultiMiner project focuses on creating robust, scalable, and transferable tools for mineral exploration, utilizing multi-source EO data across various scales and platforms (drone, airborne, spaceborne). The developed algorithms are designed to improve the accuracy and time-efficiency of mineral identification of CRMs and SRMs based on EO data. Key developments of the project, which are described in the following paragraphs, include a Mineral Mapping Algorithm, workflows for multi-scale EO data interpretation, a Mineral Prospectivity Wizard and a Generic Mine Site Monitoring algorithm.

The Mineral Mapping Algorithm (MMA) is developed for automatic spectral feature extraction from a comprehensive mineral spectral library. Hyperspectral data were acquired using SPECIM AISA Fenix system mounted on a tripod to perform terrestrial mine wall scans. The wavelength coverage is from 400 to 2500 nm and the spatial resolution of about 30 cm per pixel. Reflectance retrieval was carried out using a 95% diffuse reflecting white reference. Figure 2 shows results from *in situ* data analysis applying the spectral feature fit method by comparing mineral diagnostic spectral feature from a reference sample taken from the spectral library with the unknown pixel spectrum. The distribution shows best fit in red and low fit in dark blue colors.

Figure 2. Detailed mining wall scanning for mineral mapping: a) Open pit, NE wall, 30th July 2024, AISA Fenix, True colour image. b) Open pit 30th July 2024, AISA Fenix, magnesite abundances. c) Open pit 30th July 2024, AISA Fenix, dolomite abundances. d) Spectral profiles of magnesite and dolomite.

Workflows for multi-scale EO data interpretation are implemented to add value to data analyses by integrating various data types. The workflows are operated through a guided **Mineral Prospectivity Wizard (MPW)**. The open access demonstrator is a GUI-based step-by-step assistant (Figure 3) that guides users through various data processing and analysis steps, including pre-selection of minerals from the spectral database, displaying, processing and classifying different remote sensing image data (hyperspectral, multispectral, RGB, etc.), and defining the analysis methods, output products (e.g., mineral distribution maps, proxy maps, etc.), and machine learning algorithms. The tool harmonizes the data spectrally and spatially to enable consistent and reproducible analyses. By using the GUI, the user can process the remote sensing data in one well-structured workflow to generate the desired remote sensing products related to mineral exploration purposes.

In addition to exploration, MultiMiner develops EO solutions for mine site monitoring throughout the entire mining lifecycle, including 1) 3D/4D monitoring of composition and volume of tailings storage facilities, 2) automatic interpretation of European Ground Motion Service products, producing maps for dam stability and open pit stability, 3) algorithms and maps of ground moisture, supporting dam stability as well, 4) monitoring algorithms for water quality and acid mine drainage, 5) algorithms and maps of revegetation status, including vegetation structure and plant diversity and 6) multi-source models for atmospheric and surface dust monitoring. Encompassing most of these thematic applications, an ambitious **Generic Mine Site Monitoring algorithm (GMSM)** is developed. GMSM performs these monitoring tasks with advanced deep learning methods, combining EO foundation models with trainable adaptive decoders, making use of the vast amounts of available EO data and sparser in situ data (Figure 4).

Figure 3. The preliminary interface of the MultiMiner Mineral Prospectivity Wizard (MPW) showing how the data is handled as well as the first results. The map on the right side shows the wavelength position of the carbonate feature. Red colors mark the dolomite and the greenish color the magnesite.

Figure 4. GSM for multimodal inputs and different downstream tasks. The foundation model was pretrained using vast amount of multi-sensory EO data. The Decoder is a Temporal Attention Network (TAN), which embeds the temporal information of the input data, together with the features representation from the foundation model.

MultiMiner’s developments and results will be showcased in detail at a conference to be organized towards the end of the project. The generated tools will also be available for further exploitation and development through Github.